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Fostering Sustainable Practices Of Peace Through Peace Education: A Comprehensive Approach To Curricula Development

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This presentation focuses on peace education and curricular development, providing both a conceptual perspective on peace education and a practical framework through the PeaceEDU project. Coordinated at TAPRI, this project involves partners from Ukraine, Georgia, and Moldova, as well as several partners from the European Union. This approach begins with an understanding of peace education based on a concept note developed following needs assessments conducted in Georgia, Moldova, and Ukraine. Peace education is defined as a transformational, transformative, and polylogical learning process, both about and for peace. These three terms are defined from distinct perspectives. First, the process is transformational in that it is oriented toward understanding conflict, intended to transform modes of violent confrontation and promote a culture of peace. Second, it is transformative from a pedagogical orientation; peace education aims to educate in peaceful ways, thereby transforming the participants themselves. This involves examining not only the content of peace education but also the methods of its delivery in the classroom. Finally, it is polylogical in terms of participatory engagement, seeking to enhance the dialogic and participatory skills and virtues of participants for the purpose of conflict prevention and transformation.

The concept note emphasizes that peace education is not viewed as a single discipline or an isolated issue but is fundamentally a multidisciplinary field, aligning with many peace education and peace studies curricula worldwide. It is integrated into various courses, including psychology, social sciences, political science, and history, with the aim of promoting the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values necessary to foster peaceful relations and reduce violence. This is achieved through educational and capacity-building processes that are multidisciplinary, transversal, intersectional, relational, and cross-cultural.

Peace education constitutes a significant part of the United Nations agenda for peace, promoting peaceful relations in a multidimensional manner. The PeaceEDU project contributes to this by preventing conflicts from escalating into violence through educational systems. This involves preserving peace through peacekeeping, restoring it through peacemaking, and nurturing it through peacebuilding in the broader sense of fostering peaceful relations. The project also

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recognizes that peace education can occasionally be embedded within violent systems or even be complicit in violence; therefore, it advocates for unlearning and disrupting conventional learning modes by introducing more participatory and peaceful pedagogical methods.

This conceptual framework guides the PeaceEDU project, which is co-funded by the European Union. The objective is to support and facilitate the cultivation of sustainable peace practices in Ukraine, Georgia, and Moldova by working with higher education institutions to develop multidisciplinary peace education and peace studies courses and implementing them into existing curricula. Tampere University coordinates this project alongside twelve other partners, including the co-coordinator, Ilia State University in Tbilisi, Georgia. The consortium also includes institutions such as Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv and Kharkiv National University. In each of the three target countries, two universities and one beneficiary NGO are involved, reflecting the belief that curricular changes must be accompanied by efforts to make information accessible to the wider public. Furthermore, the project includes four EU partners in Finland, Austria, and Germany. Three of these are higher education institutions, accompanied by one NGO partner in Finland, the Peace Education Institute, which assists in transferring the knowledge and expertise found within existing peace education studies curricula in EU countries.

As previously mentioned, the primary objective is to develop and integrate peace education and peace studies into the existing curricula of partner countries. This is achieved by training teachers and educators to contribute to continuous learning and professional development, while also providing training tools and syllabi designed to impact the education system more broadly. Collaboration with NGOs is specifically aimed at raising public awareness regarding the importance of peace education and the work of university partners. Ultimately, the project aims to build community resilience and disseminate results to the wider public, with a particular focus on youth. The concept note and general principles of peace education were developed based on needs assessments conducted by partners in Ukraine, Georgia, and Moldova.

These results are analyzed to identify synergies across all three assessments while recognizing that each national context is unique and requires a tailored approach. The general results of the needs assessment highlight themes common to all three countries, such as human rights, democracy, international recognition, youth engagement, cultural diversity, sensitivity, tolerance, inclusiveness, and civic engagement. These patterns are essential for enhancing conflict transformation and social cohesion across the region. Despite these similarities, distinct priority needs were identified in each country. In Ukraine, the focus is specifically on conflict resolution, social cohesion, the promotion of human rights and democracy, tolerance, and the international recognition of Ukraine's integration into global institutions. In the case of Moldova, while conflict resolution and social cohesion remain top priorities, there is also a significant emphasis on general youth engagement and the recognition of cultural diversity. Finally, in Georgia, conflict

resolution is a primary priority alongside tolerance, inclusivity, civic engagement, and cultural sensitivity.

These themes are interconnected, and the work is collaborative. While context-specific activities occur in each country, partners work together to learn from one another and develop a cross-regional course to be implemented in all participating countries. Students from the European Union will also be able to enroll in this course, as it is a shared initiative resulting from the collective efforts of the thirteen project partners. Having reviewed the needs assessment and established the conceptual framework for peace education, the following summarizes the path forward. The development of curricula and courses remains a primary priority; however, training teachers and in-service practitioners is equally essential to ensure they are adequately prepared to deliver peace education at their universities. Various pedagogies of peace are also being explored. Study visits to Finland and the University of Innsbruck in Austria have been conducted to learn from established practices in peace studies. In these settings, non-conventional learning methods, such as role-playing exercises and case studies, are integrated.

Simultaneously, collaboration with NGOs and partners involves organizing extracurricular activities, particularly through school clubs where students can engage with peace education in non-academic or informal contexts. Cooperation with civil society aims to broaden awareness of these activities beyond individual institutions through social media and other dissemination efforts, including this presentation. This concludes the presentation. Further information regarding the project and its partners in each participating country is available on the PeaceEDU website. Interested parties are invited to engage by sending a message regarding potential collaboration or ideas for the further dissemination of project results.